

Effect of Three-Step Interview Strategy on Performance in Basic Science Concepts among Secondary School Students in Onna, Akwa Ibom State

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of three-step interview strategy on performance in basic science concepts among secondary school students in Onna Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. Two null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. Pretest, posttest non-equivalent quasi-experimental control group design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consists of all Junior Secondary School class two (II) Basic Science students during 2022/2023 academic session in Onna LGA of Akwa Ibom State. Sample size of 100 (46 Male and 54 Female) students were selected for the study. The sample size was arrived at by selecting two government coeducational secondary schools in the area of study using simple random sampling technique. The sample in each schools were explored using an intact class. Basic Science Performance Test (BSPT) and lesson note on the concept of human development for the experimental and control groups were used for data collection. The reliability of the instruments was established using Kuder Richardson KR-20 with a reliability coefficient of 0.82. Data collected were analysed using analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) statistics. Results revealed that students taught the concept of human development using three-step interview cooperative learning strategy performed significantly better than those taught using lecture teaching method. Base on the finding it was further concluded that using three-step interview cooperative learning strategy improves performance in basic science. The study therefore recommends that Basic science teachers should adopt three-step interview cooperative learning strategy in teaching and learning process in our schools.

Keywords: Three-step cooperative learning strategy, Academic Performance, Basic Science.

Introduction

The enormous importance of science in the technological, economic and political development of nations globally explains why technological attainment is often used to determine the level of development of every nation. Mathematics, Science and Technology are essential tools for socio-economic and cultural development of any nation (Usman, 2016; Babayemi & Utibe, 2017). This has led to every nation strategizing on how to develop Science and Technology to earn national recognition. The world is becoming a global village with every nation struggling to control the global market through technological innovations with capacity to attract global acceptance. Lawal (2017) stated that, science and technology provide the foundation for wealth creation and advancement of quality life. Babayemi (2014) pointed out that, science and technology is the arrowhead that determines the dimension and direction of national development. Ajewole (2015) also stated that Science and Technology have for long been recognized as the instruments par excellence for nation building and wealth creation which made every country today crave for their advancement. Akpan (2016) observed that science and technology have become crucial factors for sustainable development worldwide and have contributed immensely to the material progress of nations. The increase of scientific literacy in these years and therefore, in the current science and technology dominated society, shows that scientific literacy is considered an important goal of Science Education (Shu-Nu-Chang, 2017). Hence, science education can be considered a fundamental component of basic education, which prepares children to live in a world that is increasingly

defined by science and technology, thus the need for inclusion of Basic Science and Technology as a subject in the Nigerian school curriculum.

In Nigeria, Basic Science is one of the major subjects offered by all students in junior secondary schools. Unfortunately, the number of students offering Basic Science is more than the number of teachers employed to teach the subject in various schools. Class size is large, thus increases teachers' workload resulting in teachers' ineffectiveness (Babayemi, 2014). In addition, Olagunju and Babayemi (2014) asserted that Basic Science has the perennial problems of lack of class activities and instructional resources to teach the subject. The use of relevant instructional resources as well as carefully guided activities engages students in meaningful learning (Olagunju & Babayemi, 2014).

Basic Science and Technology teaching has a number of problems among which are poorly trained teachers, inadequacy in pedagogy and content knowledge, ill-equipped laboratories and assessment techniques (Ibe, 2018; Babayemi & Kareem, 2019). Most teachers of Basic Science and Technology have their specialization in Biology, Chemistry, Physics, Geography and Agricultural science respectively and tend to teach only content areas related to the areas of their specialization. A competent teacher has to introduce methods to develop students' scientific understanding, thinking and problem-solving abilities. This would help in solving conceptual problems. It would also result in high achievement in science than the conventional lecture method that tends to emphasize knowledge and ignores higher order thinking (Usman, 2017; Babayemi & Ahmed, 2019). Edem, Akpan and Umanah (2023) noted that the importance attributes to the vital role of science education in national development necessitates the implementation of a well-structured and organized approach to the teaching of science. In line with the above assertion, Akpan and Itighise (2021) noted that all students can learn if given the appropriate amount of time and the appropriate instructional opportunities. There is need for Nigerian science teachers to incorporate more innovative teaching strategies in teaching that can enhance high students' achievement and improve the quality of discourse during science lesson (Abdullahi, 2018; Olagunju & Babayemi, 2014).

Another major problem is the use of inappropriate teaching methods. Ibraheem and Oladele (2010) identified poor teaching method as one of the reasons for poor academic achievement. Students' educational gains, acquisition of scientific knowledge, attitudes and skills depend on the right type of instructional methodologies employed by the teacher (Babayemi, 2014). All students are not the same in every respect. They acquire learning at different time and rate. For this reason, any inappropriate method used by the teacher affects the objectives of the lesson, make students scientifically illiterate and place students' performance on a level worse than it could ever be. Akpan (2018) maintained that science education research, innovation and practices must become more responsive to the needs and attributes of the society and reflects it values. They should reflect the science that citizens and society need and support people of all ages and talents in developing positive attitude to science. Since the time of introduction of Basic Science, the problems of teaching Integrated Science still persist in the teaching and learning of Basic Science (Olagunju & Babayemi, 2014).

The innovation of students-centered strategies and instructional resources to affect qualitative teaching of science and mathematics across grade levels and subject areas, and can also accommodate a range of students' learning differences has been the major task of curriculum developers, science and mathematics educators, skilful teachers and researchers (Olagunju & Babayemi, 2014; Abasi, 2018; Edoho & Abasi, 2019; Akpan & Babayemi, 2022). An instructional situation whereby the student is featured as the active participant while the teacher assumes the roles of a facilitator, mediator and assessor of learning have been found to be superior in developing students' abilities in applying concepts to personal growth, developing positive attitudes, fostering motivation, and encouraging appropriate cognitive skills (Edoho & Abasi, 2019). Abasi, Okri and Arikpo (2022) stated that the teaching and learning of science in general and mathematics specifically, requires the discovery of innovative instructional resources that will boost students' cognitive reasoning thereby enhancing their performance and retention.

Many teachers want their students to learn, enjoy, and be engaged in their classes. A good way to create such atmosphere is to incorporate active and cooperative learning approaches into the classroom. Teachers should be able to design learning models to help students develop an understanding of concepts, reasoning, problem solving, and instructional communication. Teachers should be able to apply innovative learning strategies in their classroom instruction to encourage active participation of students in teaching and learning activities. Students being active in learning activities are expected to result in developing a positive attitude towards science which will equally boost their motivation to learn, enhance academic performance and retention in basic science and technology. Such learning strategies that promote students' active participation in the instructional process are cooperative and constructivist learning strategies. Cooperative learning refers to a variety of teaching strategies in which students work in small groups to help one another learn academic content.

However, in this research, the researcher focuses on Three-Step Interview cooperative learning strategy. Three step interview as a cooperative learning strategy is an educational approach to teaching and learning that involves groups of students

working together to solve a problem, complete a task, or create a product. Three-Step Interview is a cooperative learning strategy that consists of three stages of activities, namely: Interview – Interview - Report by conditioning students to form partners and alternately interview their partners, then report the results of the interview to other pairs. According to Barkley *et al.* (2009), in Three-Step Interview, students' pairs take turns interviewing each other and then report what they learn to another pair. The three steps (Interview-Interview-Report) are; step one: student A interviews student B; step two: student B interviews student A; step three: student A and student B, each summarizes their partner's responses for student C and D, and vice versa. The teaching steps of Three-Step Interview leads students to communicate in target language. When students interact with each other, they convey nearly all the ideas which involve all indicators of learning. Thus, Three-Step Interview strategy involves all the students to participate actively in the learning activities in the classroom.

Within existing literature, many researchers Usmedi, Hasanah and Ergusni (2020) and Calceran and Mugot (2019) have investigated on the effectiveness of three-step interview cooperative learning strategy on students' achievement in various subject areas. Their findings have established that three-step interview cooperative learning strategy showed to be an effective instructional strategies in enhancing students' learning outcomes. It is against this background that this study is aimed at investigating the effect of three-step cooperative learning strategy and gender on students' academic performance in basic science.

Ameh and Dantani (2012) reported that the observed deterioration in students' academic performance may have been contributed by teachers' persistent use of lecture method of teaching. Conventional strategies adopted by teachers at secondary school level in Nigeria have been identified as one of the major factors contributing to poor performance of students in basic science and technology. Researchers such as Atadoga and Lakpini (2013) found that the persistent low academic performance in basic science and technology is attributed to instructional strategies adopted by teachers among others. There are so many aspects of basic science and technology concepts that are difficult (Babayemi, Akpan & Emah, 2018), and yet must be learnt by students. Engaging students in a learning activities within a cooperative context would cultivate a more meaningful learning habit in the students which may bring about positive change in their academic performance.

Academic performance does not generally depend on whether the students are male and female. The concept "gender" refers to cultural attributes of both males and females (Akpochafor, 2011). Gender is a psychological experience of being a male and female. Gender in essence, is a term used to emphasise that sex inequality is not caused by the anatomic and physiological differences that characterize men and women, rather it is by an unequal and inequitable treatment socially accorded to them. The influence of gender on students' performance has a long time been a concern to many educational researchers (Ado & Abasi, 2014; Umanah & Sunday, 2022) but surprisingly no consistent results have been obtained.

Ensuring quality instruction at all levels of education is one of the core objectives of Basic Science education. These can be achieved through effective classroom interaction that create equitable chances for both male and female students to acquire right knowledge of the subject matter, positive attitudes, values, behaviour and have equal right for participating intelligently in making right decisions for their own wellbeing. Hence, it is against this background that this study aimed at investigating the effect of three-step interview cooperative learning strategy on male and female students' academic performance in Basic Science in Onna Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Basic Science plays a vital role in Nigerian science education program as it prepares pupils at the Junior Secondary level for the study of core science subjects at the Senior Secondary level which in turn brings about students' interest in science oriented courses especially at the tertiary institutions. These vital roles of the subject cannot be realized except through the effective effort of the classroom teacher (Babayemi *et al* 2023). Despite government's efforts to encourage science teaching and learning among Nigerian students right from the Primary and Junior Secondary School levels, the enrolment of students in core science subjects and science oriented courses at the Senior Secondary School level and tertiary institutions, is not encouraging (Abasi & Ado, 2021).

The problems of learning basic science may not be unconnected with the way and manner students are taught concepts therein. The nature of science predisposes teachers to teaching school science experimentally especially where necessary facilities are available. The conventional and supposed laboratory mode of teaching basic science offers rote memorization, individualism, competition and monopoly of ideas among the students which at the end result in students' poor performance and gross failures in internal and National examinations.

On the contrary, cooperative and constructivist learning strategies in science education have been found to be effective with various modes of the strategy researched and reported in literature (Edoho *et al*, 2020). It is believed that when students work in group rather than individually, they tend to understand each other better than when a teacher teaches them alone (Edoho *et al*, 2020). The three-step interview cooperative learning strategy which encourages sharing of knowledge and construction of knowledge for previous experiences is yet to be explored especially in science education in Nigeria and Akwa Ibom State

to be precise. It is against the above problem that this research aimed to provide answer to the question: what is the effect of three-step interview cooperative learning strategy, and gender on students' academic performance in basic science in Onna Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State?

Objectives of the Study

1. To determine the mean academic performance between students taught the concept human development using Three-step strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Onna Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.
2. To determine the mean academic performance between male and female students taught the concept human development using Three-step strategy in Onna Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

Research Questions

1. What is the mean academic performance between students taught the concept human development using Three-step strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Onna Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State?
2. What is the mean academic performance between male and female students taught the concept human development using Three-step strategy in Onna Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated for the study.

1. There is no significant difference in mean academic performance between students taught the concept human development using Three-step strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Onna Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.
2. There is no significant difference in academic performance between male and female students taught the concept human development using Three-step strategy in Onna Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

Methodology

The study adopted a pretest, posttest non-equivalent control group quasi-experimental design. The study was conducted in Onna Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The population for this study consisted of all junior secondary School two students during the 2023/2024 academic session in all the public secondary schools in Onna Local Government Area. Presently, there are nine (9) public secondary schools with a total enrolment of 1639 JS2 students of the 2022/2023 academic session in Onna LGA (Local Education Authority, 2023). The sample of this study consisted of 100 (46 Male and 54 Female) JSS 2 students drawn from 3 public secondary schools in Onna Local Government Area. In deriving the sample for this study, simple random sampling technique was used. From the population of 9 public secondary schools, three schools were randomly selected using balloting. From each of the schools selected, one school was randomly assigned as experimental group I (taught using three-step interview cooperative learning strategy) and the second school was randomly assigned as the control group (taught using lecture method). One JSS 2 intact class in each of the schools selected was randomly drawn to obtain sample for the study. At the end of the instructional process, all JS 2 students found in each of the intact classes became sample for the study.

For the purpose of data collection, Basic Science Performance Post-Test (BSPPT) was used as instrument in the study. Lesson plans were developed for experimental and control groups respectively. The instrument was constructed by the researcher. It has two sections A and B. Section A sought personal information of the students with respect to name of school and gender while Section B consisted of 30 multiple choice questions with four options A-D on the concept of human development drawn from JSS 2 basic science scheme of work. The instrument was subjected to content and face validity by two basic science teachers who have been teaching basic science at the junior secondary school level and an expert in Test and Measurement from the University of Uyo. To establish the reliability of the instrument, the researcher subjected the instrument for trial test using one intact class of JSS2 students drawn from a secondary school in the area of study. The school that was used to derive sample for trial testing the instrument was not part of the school sampled for this study. The reliability of the instrument was tested using Kuder Richardson KR-20 estimate and a reliability coefficient of 0.82 was obtained.

Before the instructional process commenced, the researcher first administered the pre-test to the students in the two schools and obtained their scores to ascertain their pre-entry ability before treatment. After the pretesting exercise, the researcher commenced the treatment procedure by teaching the students the concept of human development using the respective instructional packages. At the end of the instructional process, the researcher along with the class teacher in each school administered the posttest to the students in the two groups. Data that were generated from the exercise (Pretest and Posttest)

were used for descriptive statistical analysis of variables and to test the null hypotheses stated for the study at 0.05 level of significance using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA).

Results

Hypothesis one: There is no significant difference in mean academic performance between students taught the concept human development using Three-step strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Onna Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

Table 1: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of students' posttest scores classified by instructional strategies with pretest as covariate.

Source of Variation		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P
Covariates	Pretest	71.41	1	71.41	5.74*	.02
Main Effects	Method	682.07	1	341.03	27.40*	.00
Residual		1194.96	96	12.45		
Total		1948.44	99	19.68		

*= Significant @ $p < 0.05$ probability level

In Table 1, the calculated Probability value (P-value) .00 of the main effects (Method) is less than the significance level (0.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that at $P < 0.05$, there is significant difference in the mean performance scores of junior secondary school students in Basic Science taught using three-step interview cooperative learning strategy and lecture teaching method. In order to determine the direction of significance, the Least Square Difference (LSD) Post-hoc pairwise comparison test was done and the results are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: LSD posthoc pairwise comparison test of students' posttest scores classified by instructional strategies with pretest scores as covariate

(I) Methods	(J) Methods	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	P
Three Step Interview	Lecture Method	6.51*	.95	.00
Lecture Method	Three Step Interview	-6.51*	.95	.00

Table 2 shows a mean difference (6.51) between students taught using three-step interview cooperative learning strategy and lecture teaching method. The levels of significance displayed in Table 2 indicated that students taught using three-step interview cooperative learning strategy achieved significantly better than those taught using lecture teaching method.

Hypothesis two: There is no significant difference in academic performance between male and female students taught the concept human development using Three-step strategy in Onna Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

Table 3: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of male and female students' Posttest scores based on Instructional Strategies with Pretest as covariate

Source of Variation		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P
Covariates	Pretest	4.31	1	4.31	0.33*	.57
Main Effects	Methods	372.74	1	372.74	28.39	.00
	Gender	20.20	1	20.20	1.54*	.22
2-Way Interactions	Methods * Gender	1.82	1	1.82	0.14	.71
Residual		748.37	57	13.13		

Total	1147.44	61	18.81
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*= Not significant $p < 0.05$ probability level

The result in Table 3 shows the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of the difference in the achievement scores of male and female Basic science and technology students in concept of human development. The result showed that there is no significant difference in academic performance between male and female students taught the concept human development using three-step strategy in Onna Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. ($F=1.54$; $P=0.22$). Since the associated probability value of 0.22 obtained is greater than 0.05 level of significance set for decision making, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant gender difference in basic science and technology students' mean performance scores when taught the concept of human development using three-step interview cooperative learning strategy and lecture teaching method was not rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The findings with regard the difference in the mean performance scores of junior secondary school students in Basic Science and Technology taught the concept of human development using Three-Step Interview cooperative learning strategy and Lecture teaching method showed that there is a significant difference in the mean performance scores of students in Basic Science and Technology taught the concept of human development using Three-Step Interview cooperative learning strategy and Lecture teaching method. Thus, students taught using Three-step interview cooperative learning strategy performed significantly better than those taught using and Lecture teaching method. This result could be attributed to the fact that students taught using three-step interview cooperative learning strategy engaged more in cooperative interaction within their group members and with students from other groups thereby sharing ideas, correcting misconceptions and learning from others experiences. The result of this finding is in line with the findings by Usmani, Hasanah and Ergusni (2020), Calceran and Mugot (2019) who showed that students taught using three-step interview cooperative learning strategy performed better than their counterparts.

The findings with regard to the effect of instructional strategies and gender on junior secondary school students' academic performance in Basic Science and Technology taught the concept of human development showed that there exists no significant effect of instructional strategies and gender on junior secondary school students' performance in Basic Science and Technology when taught the concept of human development. Thus, the use of three-step interview cooperative learning strategy and lecture teaching method was not gender bias hence the result obtained. This result could be attributed to the fact that both male and female students within the three-step cooperative learning environment and lecture teaching method had the opportunity to interact and synergize among themselves sharing their experiences and ideas thereby learning at the same pace. The strategy encourages both male and female students' active participation in the learning process. Though there is no influence of gender on students' learning outcome with respect to the use of three-step interview cooperative learning strategy in the available literature of this study, findings from the use of other cooperative learning strategy as reviewed in the literature showed a contrasting standpoint. The result of this finding is in contrast with the findings of Nwachukwu, (2014) and Nwagbo and Okoro (2012) who showed that male students taught using cooperative learning strategy had a higher mean score than their female counterparts.

Conclusion

Based on the results obtained from this study, the researcher concluded that using instructional strategy such as three-step interview cooperative learning strategy in teaching and learning the concept of human developments in basic science provides a better insight and deeper understanding for the students as they learn from each other's experiences cooperatively and constructively. The application of these strategy boosted students' cognitive ability in learning the concept of human development thereby enhanced their performance in basic science and technology.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher considered the following recommendations relevant for the improvement of basic science and technology education.

1. Basic science and technology teachers should adopt three-step interview cooperative learning strategy in teaching and learning process in our schools. If the teaching and learning of basic science and technology is to gain popularity, capture the attention of the learners and challenge their intellect, the content must be made more appealing in terms of the instructional strategies used. This is done by creating an activity based classroom instruction through the practice of three-step interview cooperative learning strategy.

2. Teachers should be trained and re-trained on the techniques of utilizing three-step interview cooperative learning strategy in the teaching of basic science and technology. This process should be done through organizing seminars, workshops, symposiums, conferences and in-service training etc.

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